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NOVEL VESICULAR DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS CHARECTARISING THE STATE OF ART TECHNOLOGIES: AN UPDATED REVIEW ON NIOSOMES

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ABSTRACT

A niosome is a non-ionic surfactant-based liposome. Niosomes are formed mostly by cholesterol incorporation as an excipient and having more penetrating characteristic than the previous preparations of emulsions. Niosomes and liposomes are bioequivalent in drug delivery systems, the potentiality to drug efficacy as compared with that of free drug. Niosomes are preferred over liposomes because the former exhibit high chemical stability and these are biodegradable, biocompatible nonimmunogenic and exhibit flexibility in their structural characterization. Niosomes have been widely evaluated for controlled release and targeted delivery for the treatment of immunological diseases. The review representing that encapsulation of drug in vesicular system can be predicted to prolong the existence of drug in the systemic circulation and enhance penetration into target tissue and reduce toxicity in a state of art technologies.

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INTRODUCTION

Paul Ehrlich, in 1909, initiated the development for targeted delivery when he envisaged a drug delivery mechanism that would target directly to diseased cell. Drug targeting can be defined as the ability to direct a therapeutic agent specifically to desired site of action with little or no interaction with non-target tissue. Vesicles prepared from self-assembly of hydrated non-ionic surfactants molecules are called niosomes. These types of vesicles were first reported in the cosmetic industries. Nonionic surfactants used in the formation of niosomes are polyglyceryl alkyl ether, glucosyl dialkyl ether, crown ether, polyoxyethylenealkyl ether, ester-linked surfactants, and steroid-linked surfactants, spans, and tweens series. Niosomes preparation is affected by processes variables, nature of surfactants, presence of membrane additives and nature of drug to be encapsulated [1].

DEFINITION

Niosomes are essentially nonionic surfactant based multilamellar or unilamellar vesicles in which an aqueous solution of solute is entirely enclosed by a membrane resulted from the organization of surfactant macro molecules bilayers. Nonionic surfactant vesicle results from the self-assembly of hydrated surfactant monomers.

STRUCTURE OF NIOSOME

L'Oreals reported alkyl and dialkyl polyglycerol ethers as vesicle forming nonionic surfactant. A typical niosome vesicle would consist of a vesicle forming amphiphile i.e. a non-ionic surfactant such as Span-60, which is usually stabilized by the addition of cholesterol and a small amount of anionic surfactant such as diacetyl phosphate, which also helps in stabilizing the vesicle [2]. Niosomes may be unilamellar or multilamellar depending on the method used to prepare them. The niosome is made of a surfactant bilayer with its hydrophilic ends exposed on the outside and inside of the vesicle, while the hydrophobic chains face each other within the bilayer. Hence, the vesicle holds hydrophilic drugs within the space enclosed in the vesicle, while hydrophobic drugs are embedded within the bilayer itself [3]. The figure below will give a better idea of what a niosome looks like and where the drug is located within the vesicle.

Figure No 1: Diagrammatic representation of Niosome vesicle.

Advantages of Niosomes

- The vesicle suspension being water based offers greater patient compliance over oil based systems
- Since the structure of the niosome offers place to accommodate hydrophilic, lipophilic as well as amphiphilic drug moieties, they can be used for a variety of drugs.
- The characteristics such as size, lamellarity etc. of the vesicle can be varied depending on the requirement.
- The vesicles can act as a depot to release the drug slowly and offer a controlled release.

Salient Features of Niosomes

- Niosomes can entrap solutes in a manner analogous to liposomes.
- Niosomes are osmotically active and stable.
- Niosomes possess an infra structure consisting of hydrophobic and hydrophilic mostly together and so also accommodate the drug molecules with a wide range of solubility.
- Niosomes exhibits flexibility in their structural characteristics (composition, fluidity and size) and can be designed according to the desired situation.
- Niosome can improve the performance of the drug molecules by delayed clearance from the circulation.
- Improve bioavailability to the particular site, just by protecting the drug from biological environment.
- Offer controlled delivery of drug at a particular site [4].
- No special conditions are required for handling and storage of Niosomes.

Disadvantages of Niosomes

1. Physical instability
2. Aggregation
3. Fusions
4. Leaking of entrapped drug
5. Hydrolysis of encapsulated drugs which limiting the shelf life of the dispersion.

TYPES OF NIOSOMAL SYSTEMS**Small Unilamellar vesicles**

(SUV, size 0.025-0.05 μm) are commonly produced by sonication, and French Press procedures. Ultrasonic electrocapillary emulsification or solvent dilution techniques can be used to prepare SUVs.

Multilamellar vesicles

(MLV, size $>0.05 \mu\text{m}$) exhibit increased-trapped volume and equilibrium solute distribution, and require hand-shaking method. They show variations in lipid compositions [5].

Large unilamellar vesicles

(LUV, size $>0.10 \mu\text{m}$), the injections of lipids solubilised in an organic solvent into an aqueous buffer, can result in spontaneous formation of LUV. But the better method of preparation of LUV is Reverse phase evaporation, or by Detergent solubilisation method [6].

COMPOSITIONS OF NIOSOMES:**Non-ionic surfactants:**

The non-ionic surfactants orient themselves in bilayer lattices where the polar or hydrophobic heads align facing aqueous bulk (media) while the hydrophobic head or hydrocarbon segments align in such a way that the interaction with the aqueous media would be minimized. To attain thermodynamic stability, every bilayer folds over itself as continuous membrane i.e. forms vesicles so that hydrocarbon /water interface remains.

Mainly following types of non-ionic surfactants are used for the formation of niosomes

a) Alkyl ethers: L'Oreal described some surfactants for the preparation of niosomes containing drugs/chemicals as

- 1) Surfactant-I (Mol.Wt.473) is C16 monoalkyl glycerol ether with average of three glycerol units.
- 2) Surfactant-II (Mol.Wt.972) is diglycerol ether with average of the seven glycerol units.
- 3) Surfactant III (Mol.Wt.393) is ester linked surfactant. Other than alkyl glycerol, alkyl glycosides and alkyl ethers bearing polyhydroxyl head groups are also used in formulation of niosomes [7].

b) Alkyl esters: Sorbitan esters are most preferred surfactant used for the preparation of niosomes amongst this category of surfactants. Vesicles prepared by the polyoxyethylene sorbitan monolaurate are relatively soluble than other surfactant vesicles. For example, polyoxyethylene (polysorbate 60) has been utilized for encapsulation of diclofenac sodium.

c) Alkyl amides: Alkyl amide (e.g. galactosides and glucosides) have been utilized to produce niosomal vesicles.

d) Fatty acid and amino acid compounds: Long chain fatty acids and amino acid moieties have also been used in some niosomes preparation [8].

Cholesterol

Sterols are important components of the cell membrane and their presence in membrane affect the bilayer fluidity and permeability. Cholesterol is a sterol derivative, which is mainly used for the formulation of niosomes. Although it may not show any role in the formation of bilayer, its importance in formation of niosomes and manipulation of layer characteristics cannot be discarded. In general, incorporation of cholesterol affects properties of niosomes like membrane permeability, rigidity, encapsulation efficiency, ease of rehydration of freeze dried niosomes and their toxicity [9]. It prevents the vesicle aggregation by the inclusion of molecules that stabilize the system against the formation of aggregates by repulsive steric or electrostatic forces that leads to the transition from the gel to the liquid phase in niosome systems. As a result of this, the niosome become less leaky in nature [10].

Formulation aspects of Niosomes

Niosomes are formed by self-assembly of non-ionic surfactants in aqueous media as spherical, unilamellar, multilamellar system and polyhedral structures in addition to inverse structures which appear only in non-aqueous solvent.

Nature of surfactants

The non-ionic surfactants are preferred because the irritation power of surfactants decreases in the following order: cationic > anionic > ampholytic > non-ionic. The ester type surfactants are chemically less stable than ether type surfactants and the former is less toxic than the latter because ester-linked surfactant is degraded by esterase to triglycerides and fatty acid *in vivo*. The surfactants with alkyl chain length from C12-C18 are suitable for the preparation of niosome. Span series surfactants having hydrophilic lipophilic balance (HLB) number of between 4-8 can form vesicles [11].

Charge inducer

Charge inducer is used to impart charge on the vesicles to increase its stability by preventing fusion of vesicles and providing higher value of zeta potential. The commonly used positively charge inducers are stearylamine, cetyl pyridinium chloride and negatively charge inducers are lipoamino acid and dicetyl phosphate. Drug entrapment efficiency varied with the charge and the percent entrapment efficiency was found to be 43.75%, 51.23% and 36.26% for neutral, positively charged and negatively charged niosomes, respectively. The positively charged niosomes, although showed good corneal permeability and IOP lowering capacity, were however seemed to be inappropriate in terms of the corneal cell toxicity [12].

Bioadhesive polymer

Bioadhesive polymers are the other membrane additives that are used to provide some additional properties to the niosomes. Carbopol 934P-coated niosomal formulation of ACZ, prepared from Span 60, cholesterol, stearylamine or dicetyl phosphate exhibited more tendency for the reduction of intraocular pressure compared to that of a marketed formulation [13].

FORMATION OF NIOSOMES FROM PRONIOSOMES:

The method of producing niosomes is to coat a water-soluble carrier such as sorbitol with surfactant. The result of the coating process is a dry formulation. In which each water-soluble particle is covered with a thin film of dry surfactant. This preparation is termed "Proniosomes" [14].

$$T > T_m$$

Where,

T = Temperature

T_m = mean phase transition temperature

Figure 2: Characterization of Proniosomes.

Figure 3: Lab scale preparation of Proniosomes.

PREPARATION METHODS OF NIOSOMES

The various methods of preparation based on the desired sizes of the vesicles and their distribution, number of double layers, entrapment efficiency of the aqueous phase and permeability of vesicle membrane. That are similar to preparation of liposomes.

Preparation of Small Unilamellar Vesicles

Sonication:

The sonication may be accomplished using probe sonicator where simple size is small volume. However, for larger sample volume bath sonicator is suitable [15].

Preparation steps

Drug in buffer + surfactant/cholesterol in 10 ml

Above mixture is sonicated for 3 mints at 60oC using titanium probe yielding Niosomes.

Figure 4: Exposure of MLVs to ultrasonic irradiation for producing small vesicles.

(b)Micro fluidization:

Micro fluidization is a recent technique used to prepare unilamellar vesicles of defined size distribution. This method is based on submerged jet principle in which two fluidized streams interact at ultra-high velocities, in precisely defined micro channels within the interaction chamber. The impingement of thin liquid sheet along a common front is arranged such that the energy supplied to the system remains within the area of niosomes formation. The result is a greater uniformity, smaller size and better reproducibility of niosomes formed [16].

Preparation steps

Two ultra-high-speed jets inside interaction chamber
 ↓
 Impingement of thin layer of Liquid in micro channels
 ↓
 Formation of uniform Niosomes.

Preparation of Multilamellar Vesicles**Hand shaking method (Thin film hydration technique):**

The mixture of vesicles forming ingredients like surfactant and cholesterol are dissolved in a volatile organic solvent (diethyl ether, chloroform or methanol) in a round bottom flask. The organic solvent is removed at room temperature (20°C) using rotary evaporator leaving a thin layer of solid mixture deposited on the wall of the flask. The dried surfactant film can be rehydrated with aqueous phase at 0-60°C with gentle agitation. This process forms typical multilamellar niosomes[17].

Preparation steps:

Surfactant + cholesterol + solvent
 ↓
 Remove organic solvent at Room temperature
 ↓
 Thin layer formed on the Walls of flask
 ↓
 Film can be rehydrated to form multilamellar Niosomes.

Figure 5: Formulation of niosomal dispersion.

Trans-membrane pH gradient (inside acidic) drug uptake process (remote loading):

Surfactant and cholesterol are dissolved in chloroform. The solvent is then evaporated under reduced pressure to obtain a thin film on the wall of the round-bottom flask. The film is hydrated with 300 mM citric acid (pH 4.0) by vortex mixing. The multilamellar vesicles are frozen and thawed three times and later sonicated. To this niosomal suspension, aqueous solution containing 10 mg/ml of drug is added and vortexed. The pH of the sample is then raised to 7.0-7.2 with 1M disodium phosphate. This mixture is later heated at 60°C for 10 minutes to produce the desired multilamellar vesicles[18].

Preparation steps**Preparation of Large Unilamellar Vesicles****Reverse phase evaporation technique (REV):**

In this method, cholesterol and surfactant are dissolved in a mixture of ether and chloroform¹⁶. An aqueous phase containing drug is added to this and the resulting two phases are sonicated at 4-5°C. The clear gel formed is further sonicated after the addition of a small amount of phosphate buffered saline. The organic phase is removed at 40°C under low pressure. The resulting viscous niosome suspension is diluted with phosphate-buffered saline and heated in a water bath at 60°C for 10 min to yield niosomes^[19].

Preparation steps

Figure 6: Rotary evaporation method.

Ether injection method:

The ether injection method is essentially based on slow injection of niosomal ingredients in diethyl ether through a 14-gauge needle at the rate of approximately 0.25 ml/min into a preheated aqueous phase maintained at 60°C [13,17]. The probable reason behind the formation of larger unilamellar vesicles is that the slow vaporization of solvent results in an ether gradient extending towards the interface of aqueous-nonaqueous interface. The former may be responsible for the formation of the bilayer structure. The disadvantages of this method are that a small amount of ether is frequently present in the vesicles suspension and is difficult to remove [20].

Preparation steps

Surfactant is dissolved in diethyl ether
 ↓
 Then injected in warm water maintained at 60°C through a 14-gauge needle
 ↓
 Ether is vaporized to form single layered niosome.

(iv) Miscellaneous

Multiple membrane extrusion method:

Mixture of surfactant, cholesterol and dicetyl phosphate in chloroform is made into thin film by evaporation. The film is hydrated with aqueous drug polycarbonate membranes, solution and the resultant suspension extruded through which are placed in series for upto 8 passages. It is a good method for controlling niosome size [21].

(b) Emulsion method

The oil in water (o/w) emulsion is prepared from an organic solution of surfactant, cholesterol, and an aqueous solution of the drug [18,19]. The organic solvent is then evaporated, leaving niosomes dispersed in the aqueous phase.

(c) Lipid injection method

This method does not require expensive organic phase. Here, the mixture of lipids and surfactant is first melted and then injected into a highly agitated heated aqueous phase containing dissolved drug. Here, the drug can be dissolved in molten lipid and the mixture will be injected into agitated, heated aqueous phase containing surfactant [22].

(d) The “bubble” method:

It is novel technique for the one step preparation of liposome's and niosomes without the use of organic solvents. The bubbling unit consists of round-bottomed flask with three necks positioned in water bath to control the temperature. Water-cooled reflux and thermometer is positioned in the first and second neck and nitrogen supply through the third neck. Cholesterol and surfactant are dispersed together in this buffer (pH 7.4) at 70°C, the dispersion mixed for 15 seconds with high shear homogenizer and immediately afterwards “bubbled” at 70°C using nitrogen gas [23].

Separation of Untrapped Drug

The removal of untrapped solute from the vesicles can be accomplished by various techniques, which include

Dialysis

The aqueous niosomal dispersion is dialyzed in dialysis tubing against suitable dissolution medium (phosphate buffer or normal saline or glucose solution) at room temperature[24]. The samples are withdrawn from the medium at suitable time intervals, centrifuged and analyzed for drug content using suitable method (U.V. spectroscopy, HPLC etc.).

Gel Filtration

The untrapped drug is removed by gel filtration of niosomal dispersion through a Sephadex-G-50 column and eluted with suitable mobile phase and analyzed with suitable analytical techniques.

Centrifugation

The niosomal suspension is centrifuged and the supernatant is separated. The pellet is washed and then resuspended to obtain a niosomal suspension free from untrapped drug [25].

CHARACTERIZATION OF NIOSOMES

Size

Shape of niosomal vesicles is assumed to be spherical, and their mean diameter can be determined by using laser light scattering method[28]. Also, diameter of these vesicles can be determined by using electron microscopy, molecular sieve chromatography, ultracentrifugation, photon correlation microscopy, optical microscopy and freeze fracture electron microscopy. Freeze thawing (keeping vesicles suspension at -20°C for 24 hrs and then heating to ambient temperature) of Niosomes increases the vesicle diameter, which might be attributed to fusion of vesicles during the cycle[26].

Scanning electron microscopy

Particle size of niosome is very important characteristic. The surface morphology (roundness, smoothness, and formation of aggregates) and the size distribution of niosome were studied by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Niosomes were sprinkled on to the double-sided tape that was affixed on aluminum stubs. The aluminum stub was placed in the vacuum chamber of a scanning electron microscope (XL 30 ESEM with EDAX, Philips, Netherlands). The samples were observed for morphological characterization using a gaseous secondary electron detector (working pressure: 0.8 torr, acceleration voltage: 30.00 KV) XL 30, (Philips, Netherlands)[27].

Optical Microscopy

The niosome were mounted on glass slides and viewed under a microscope (Medilux-207RII, Kyowa-Getner, Ambala, India) with a magnification of 1200X for morphological observation after suitable dilution. The photomicrograph of the preparation also obtained from the microscope by using a digital SLR camera.

Entrapment efficiency

Entrapment efficiency of the niosomal dispersion in can be done by separating the untrapped drug by dialysis centrifugation or gel filtration as described above and the drug remained entrapped in niosome is determined by complete vesicle disruption using 50% n-propanol or 0.1% Triton X-100 and analyzing the resultant solution by appropriate assay method for the drug[28]. Where,

$$EE = \frac{\text{amount entrapped}}{\text{total amount added}} \times 100$$

Bilayer Formation

Assembly of non-ionic surfactants to form a bilayer vesicle is characterized by an X-cross formation under light polarization microscopy.

Measurement of Angle of repose

The angle of repose of dry niosome powder was measured by a funnel method. The niosome powder was poured into a funnel which was fixed at a position so that the 13mm outlet orifice of the funnel is 5cm above a level black surface. The powder flows down from the funnel to form a cone on the surface and the angle of repose was then calculated by measuring the height of the cone and the diameter of its base[29].

Membrane Rigidity

Membrane rigidity can be measured by means of mobility of fluorescence probe as a function of temperature.

Number of Lamellae

This is determined by using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, small angle X-ray scattering and electron microscopy[30].

Osmotic shock

The change in the vesicle size can be determined by osmotic studies. Niosomes formulations are incubated with hypotonic, isotonic, hypertonic solutions for 3 hours. Then the changes in the size of vesicles in the formulations are viewed under optical microscopy.

In Vitro Release Study

A method of *in vitro* release rate study has been reported with the help of dialysis tubing. A dialysis sac is washed and soaked in distilled water[31]. The vesicle suspension is pipetted into a bag made up of the tubing and sealed. The bag containing the vesicles is then placed in 200 ml buffer solution in a 250-ml beaker with constant shaking at 25°C or 37°C. At various time intervals, the buffer is analyzed for the drug content by an appropriate assay method. In another method, isoniazid-encapsulated niosomes are separated by gel filtration on Sephadex G-50 powder kept in double distilled water for 48 h for swelling[32]. At first, 1ml of prepared niosome suspension is placed on the top of the column and elution is carried out using normal saline. Niosome encapsulated isoniazid elutes out first as a slightly dense, white opalescent suspension followed by free drug. Separated niosomes are filled in a dialysis tube to which a sigma dialysis sac is attached to one end. The dialysis tube is suspended in phosphate buffer of pH (7.4), stirred with a magnetic stirrer, and samples are withdrawn at specific time intervals and analyzed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method[33].

In Vivo Release Study

Albino rats are used for this study. These rats are subdivided into groups. Niosomal suspension used for *in vivo* study is injected intravenously (through tail vein) using appropriate disposal syringe.

Stability studies

To determine the stability of niosomes, the optimized batch was stored in airtight sealed vials at different temperatures. Surface characteristics and percentage drug retained in niosomes and niosomes derived from proniosomes were selected as parameters for evaluation of the stability, since instability of the formulation would reflect in drug leakage and a decrease in the percentage drug retained. The niosomes were sampled at regular intervals of time (0,1,2, and 3 months), observed for color change, surface characteristics and tested for the percentage drug retained after being hydrated to form niosomes and analyzed by suitable analytical methods (UV spectroscopy, HPLC methods etc).

Applications of niosome

The application of niosome technology is widely varied and can be used to treat a number of diseases. There are very few niosomal formulations found in market. But some experimentally evaluated applications of niosomal formulation identified in literatures, either proven or under research, are listed below.

Drug targeting

One of the most useful aspects of niosomes is their ability to target drugs. Niosomes can be used to target drugs to the reticulo-endothelial system. The reticulo-endothelial system (RES) preferentially takes up niosome vesicles. The uptake of niosomes is controlled by circulating serum factors called opsonins. These opsonins mark the niosome for clearance. Such localization of drugs is utilized to treat tumors in animals known to metastasize to the liver and spleen. This localization of drugs can also be used for treating parasitic infections of the liver.

Niosomes can also be utilized for targeting drugs to organs other than the RES. A carrier system (such as antibodies) can be attached to niosomes (as immunoglobulins bind readily to the lipid surface of the niosome) to target them to specific organs. Many cells also possess the intrinsic ability to recognize and bind specific carbohydrate determinants, and this can be exploited by niosomes to direct carrier system to particular cells.

Delivery of peptide drugs

Oral peptide drug delivery has long been faced with a challenge of bypassing the enzymes which would break down the peptide. Use of niosomes to successfully protect the peptides from gastrointestinal peptide breakdown is being investigated. In an *in vitro* study, oral delivery of a vasopressin derivative entrapped in niosomes showed that entrapment of the drug significantly increased the stability of the peptide.

Use in studying immune response

Due to their immunological selectivity, low toxicity and greater stability; niosomes are being used to study the nature of the immune response provoked by antigens[34].

Niosomes as carriers for hemoglobin

Niosomes can be used as carriers for hemoglobin within the blood. The niosome vesicle is permeable to oxygen and hence can act as a carrier for hemoglobin in anemic patients.

Transdermal drug delivery systems utilizing niosome

One of the most useful aspects of niosome is that they greatly enhance the uptake of drugs through the skin. Transdermal drug delivery utilizing niosomal technology is widely used in cosmetics; in fact, it was one of the first uses of the niosomes. Topical use of niosome entrapped antibiotics to treat acne is done. The penetration of the drugs through the skin is greatly increased as compared to un-entrapped drug.

Recently, transdermal vaccines utilizing niosomal technology is also being researched. Niosomes (along with liposomes and transfersomes) can be utilized for topical immunization using tetanus toxoid. However, the current technology in niosomes allows only a weak immune response, and thus more research needs to be done in this field[35].

Ophthalmic drug delivery

It is difficult to achieve excellent bioavailability of drug from ocular dosage form like ophthalmic solution, suspension and ointment due to the tear production, impermeability of corneal epithelium, non-productive absorption and transient residence time. But to achieve good bioavailability of drug various vesicular systems are proposed to be use, in experimental level, like niosomes, liposomes. Bioadhesive-coated niosomal formulation of acetazolamide prepared from span 60, cholesterol stearylamine or dicetyl phosphate exhibits more tendencies for reduction of intraocular pressure as compared to marketed formulation (Dorzolamide). The chitosan-coated niosomal formulation timolol maleate (0.25%) exhibits more effect for reduction intraocular pressure as compared to a marketed formulation with less chance of cardiovascular side effects.

Other applications

Diagnostic imaging with niosome

Niosomal system can be used as diagnostic agents. Conjugated niosomal formulation of gadobenate dimeglumine with [N-palmitoyl-glucosamine (NPG)], PEG 4400, and both PEG and NPG exhibit significantly improved tumor targeting of an encapsulated paramagnetic agent assessed with MR imaging.

Niosome formulation as a brain targeted delivery system for the vasoactive intestinal peptide (VIP)

Radiolabeled VIP-loaded glucose-bearing niosomes were injected intravenously to mice. Encapsulated VIP within glucose-bearing niosomes exhibits higher VIP brain uptake as compared to control. Niosomes can also be utilized for sustained drug release and localized drug action to greatly increase the safety and efficacy of many drugs. Toxic drugs which need higher doses can possibly be delivered safely using niosomal encapsulation. It is obvious that niosome appears to be a well preferred drug delivery system over liposome as niosome being stable and economic. Also, niosomes have great drug delivery potential for targeted delivery of anti-cancer, anti-infective agents. Drug delivery potential of niosome can enhance by using novel concepts like proniosomes, disomes and aspasome. Niosomes also serve better aid in diagnostic imaging and as a vaccine adjuvant [36].

Marketed products

Lancome has come out with a variety of anti-ageing products with niosomes.

L'Oreal is also conducting research on anti-ageing cosmetic products.

CONCLUSION

The concept of incorporating the drug into niosomes for a better targeting of the drug at appropriate tissue destination is widely accepted by researches and academicians. Niosomes represent a promising drug delivery module. They present a structure like liposome and hence they can represent alternative vesicular systems with respect to liposomes, due to the niosome ability to encapsulate different type of drugs within their multienvironmental structure. Niosomes are thoughts to the better candidate's drug delivery as compared to liposomes due to various factors like cost, stability etc. various type of drug deliveries can be possible using niosomes like targeting, ophthalmic, topical, parenteral, etc. This review concluded that the encapsulation of drug in vesicular system can be predicted to prolong the existence of drug in the systemic circulation and enhance penetration into target tissue and reduce toxicity in a state of art technologies in the future generating dosage forms.

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